

TEACHING ENGLISH IN NON-PHILOLOGICAL CLASSES.

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Abstract; In this article is discussed, the successful and effective results depend on educational process and materials for class in teaching English.

Key words; English, teaching, ESP, CEFR, language, competence

Nowadays the English language became one of primary language and there are systems to teach language effectively. The above mentioned standards, namely State Educational Standard a special attention is paid to formation of harmoniously developed, highly educated, modern thinking generation, able to take responsibility for the fate of the Homeland. The CEFR is intended to provide a shared basis for reflection and communication among the different partners in the field, including those involved in teacher education and in the elaboration of language syllabuses, curriculum guidelines, textbooks, examinations, etc., across the member states of the Council of Europe. It is offered to users as a descriptive tool that allows them to reflect on their decisions and practice, and to situate and co-ordinate their efforts, as appropriate, for the benefit of language learners in their specific contexts.

The descriptors included in the CEFR also cover the cultural context in which language is set. The framework also describes levels of proficiency which allow learners' progress to be measured at a definite stage of language learning and on a life-long basis. The uniqueness of descriptors, flexibility of the system set within the CEFR made the framework popular across European countries and a number of non-European countries including Uzbekistan. Now it is officially established that the requirements of CEFR. It is intended to provide a basis for the development of syllabuses, curricula, textbooks and tests. The impact of this document has been very

deep in a range of areas in language, like listening, reading, speaking, and writing but main tools are teaching and testing. Actually all the aspects connected with foreign language teaching are covered by CEFR. The foreign language instruction of the students a university level should be focused and based on the field of their qualification. There is no doubt that teaching English conversation is the most important part of language learning. It is clear to teachers that students need English to communicate first and foremost therefore they must have more conversation practice in language classroom. It is common practice for general-purpose second foreign language program to incorporate the teaching of speaking skills. The recognition of speaking as a «crucial part» of a second language curriculum is reflected in general methodology texts», as well as in «second language syllabus. Speaking is the process of building and sharing meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, in a variety of contexts. Despite of its importance, teaching speaking has been undervalued for many years. English language teachers have continued to teach speaking just as a repetition of drills and memorization of artificial dialogues which purport to be developing learners' speaking skills.

As a result, many English language learners have developed the ability to speak both accurately and appropriately. In the other words, they are able «to speak reasonably correct and even fluent English but they are unable to engage in «on-going, interactive, mentally satisfying conversation. They don't take the initiative to say more, they satisfy themselves with short answers, they are not able to keep up long turns in conversation due to a lack of conversational skills. The ability to take part in a conversation is «believed to be a part of learner's communicative competence, the ultimate goal of second language learning. Therefore, teaching conversational skills in the frame of teaching speaking can improve learners' confidence how to communicate in an informal setting using basic vocabulary and sentence structures. This is the way the learner's communicative competence is developed. Teaching conversation is the highest phase of the language learning. CEFR illustrates in a detailed and comprehensive way what language learners have

to learn to do in order to use a language for communication and what knowledge and skills they have to develop in order to be able to act effectively in the target language. To practice with foreign language is difficult process. In CEFR program's main approach is student-learner approach, because hero of the lesson is student not a teacher. Basic part of this approach is motivation. Motivation has been found to be vital to development of learner participation and success. Individual motivation is related to mastery achievement because, teaching and practicing with language take much time, patience and there are few requirements to learn it. To understand the requirements of language is willingness to adapt these requirements, differentiate the foreign language for specific purposes. There two ways practicing language: English Language Teaching and English Specific Purposes. In both types, the basic aim is to practice and give samples from real life situations. ESP students are usually learners who already have some conform with English and students are learning the language in order to communicate a set of professional skills and to perform particular job-related, study-related functions.

An ESP program is therefore built on a task of purposes, needs and the functions for which English is required. ESP's important concentration meets more on language in context than on teaching grammar and language structures. It includes subjects varying from tourism or computer science to accounting and business management. The ESP program purpose is that English is not taught as a subject separated from the students' real world (or wishes); instead of this, it is integrated into a subject matter area important to the students and learners.

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